
ENHANCING NIGERIA'S GDP THROUGH RURAL INFRASTRUCTURE: INSIGHTS FROM DAWAKIN-TOFA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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Abstract

Nigeria has long struggled to revamp its economy despite being richly endowed with natural and human resources. The country remains among the least developed globally, with a large proportion of its citizens living below the poverty line. While successive governments have introduced various policies and initiatives to improve socio-economic conditions, widespread poverty and developmental challenges persist. Economic growth, as measured by Gross Domestic Product (GDP), is closely linked to both a vibrant economy and the provision of adequate infrastructure. Rural areas, in particular, play a critical role in national development by supplying raw materials, sustaining agricultural production, and supporting trade. Historically, they were central to the colonial economy and remain vital to Nigeria's economic landscape today. This study investigates the role of socio-economic infrastructural development in rural Nigeria as a pathway to improving GDP, with Dawakin Tofa Local Government Area of Kano State serving as a case study due to its extensive agricultural and trading activities. Findings highlight the need for deliberate government intervention in infrastructure provision and community engagement. The study recommends that policymakers align developmental projects with the genuine needs of rural dwellers, ensuring consistent communication and inclusivity in governance. By addressing infrastructural gaps and enhancing rural productivity, Nigeria can stimulate sustainable economic growth and bring governance closer to the people.

Keywords: *Rural Development, Infrastructure, Economic Growth, Gross Domestic Product, Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Research

The provision of socio – economic infrastructure in developing countries has not been given the much desired attention by successive governments. This problem has been more evident in Nigeria amongst other least developed African countries. The development of infrastructure in many nations is the creation of basic fundamental services to enhance economic growth and improve quality of life. Most if not all developed nations have passed through periods of rigorous building of infrastructures that have improved efficiency and competitiveness (Davies et al, 2019). During the Industrial Revolution in Europe, the

Europeans recognized the important role which infrastructure play in boosting their economy, hence the large investment on infrastructural development. This also played out very well during colonialism in Africa when the colonialists realized that they would find it difficult in fully exploiting their areas of interests, unless certain infrastructures such as roads, rails are put in place to facilitate the movement of goods and services being produced in their colonies.

According to Kabiru (2016), Nigeria loses between ₦133.8 billion and ₦175 billion due to increased vehicles operating cost, delayed turn around, increased travel time as well as reduction in asset value. There is also human cost as about 80% of injuries in Nigeria are road traffic accident (RTA) – related, making it the country with the second largest RTA fatalities among 193 countries of the world. Nwaneri (2019) submitted that Nigeria loses an estimated ₦3.5 trillion yearly due to poor ports infrastructure alone. The implication of poor state of infrastructure has been low Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the country and thus there is an unending cycle of poverty, poor living standards within the country. It also further portrays Nigeria as a costly place to do business.

Infrastructure has for a long time been an important and essential part of human activities and has also been regarded by scholars as a panacea for socio – economic development. Infrastructure is regarded as being the engine room of socio – economic growth due to the fact that it propels all facets of socio – economic activities in both developing and developed countries. It is often believed that a country with good and essential infrastructural system to support the growth and development of other sectors of the economy such as agriculture, commerce and industry has the potential of being an economic world power. These infrastructures include means of transportation, communication, schools, health facilities and services, amongst others.

The success or other wise of economic policies and plans depends largely on the available resources and enabling environment. Resources such as capital, manpower and technology are necessary inputs and the sources of economic growth endeavours largely depend on the available enabling environment as defined in part by the available infrastructure. Most Nigerians see agriculture as the most legitimate source of livelihood. Agriculture is the oldest occupation known to man and as such, most Nigerians engaged in it live in the rural area where it is predominantly being practiced. Kano State is one of the most prominent Northern Nigerian States and it is well – known for its agrarian and trading activities. Created by the military government of General Yakubu Gowon in 1967, the State currently has 44 local Government Areas (LGAs). Dawakin-Tofa LGA is one of them and the main sources of livelihood of this highly rural area are agriculture and trading activities. The entire State is the most irrigated state in Nigeria (Kano State Ministry of Health, 2013). This has been encouraged over the years so as to enhance the economic activities of the people.

Scholars and commentators have stated that the provision of infrastructure is generally viewed as being of vital importance to the socio –economic transformation of rural Nigeria. Thus, the responsibility of Government is to provide and preserve all forms of infrastructure by financing and maintaining them.

Good infrastructure helps to raise productivity and lower costs in the directly productive activities of the economy, but it has to be expanded fast enough to meet the demand for infrastructure in the early stages of development (Kim, 2006).

Research Problem

The availability of adequate and efficient infrastructures in the society boosts a nation's success in the growth of its economy, production diversification, population growth sustenance, dipping poverty and enhancing environmental conditions. With the poor state of infrastructures in developing countries such as Nigeria, efforts to grow the economy have proven to be a mirage. Accordingly, one of the most important limiting factors to economic growth and the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in several developing countries is the lack of infrastructure (Davies et al, 2019). Investment in infrastructure resulted into more than fifty percent of the improved growth performance in Africa between 1990 to 2005 and further led to an increment in businesses.

The reduction or total obliteration of the phenomenon called poverty is the major challenge confronting African countries. If the coefficients such as education, health care services, extension contacts amongst others are all negative, it suggests that they reduced inefficiency in the production of other aspects of the economy such as agriculture (Ugbabe et al, 2017).

Nigeria has the basic needed natural and human resources to develop her infrastructure but the country is characterized by different cases of inadequate infrastructures ranging from poor health care services, epileptic educational system, shortage/irregular power supply, bad roads and poor telecommunication services amongst others. This plethora of inadequacies have been discussed and supported by various findings. The level of underdevelopment of infrastructure in Nigeria has so much affected every facet of the society ranging from educational institutions, industries, hospitals and other private and public enterprises.

Successive Nigerian Governments have invested heavily in the development of infrastructure and yet there is still gross underdevelopment in the country and the economy is still in bad state.

The situation implies that Nigeria either hasn't done enough or has missed it somewhere. It is estimated that a minimum of US\$5 billion a year would be needed for the next 10 years to maintain and expand all types of infrastructure in Nigeria (Alli, 2018). The need to wriggle the country out of its present state of dependency has further buttressed the need for the country to ensure that its infrastructure is in good state so as to enhance socio-economic transformation.

Seeing how important the provision of infrastructure is to the economic growth of the nation's economy, this research study is geared towards assessing the gaps in the already existing socio – economic infrastructures; how they have impacted on economic growth and what can still be done.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this research study is to assess the impact of socio – economic infrastructural development as a panacea for improving Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product, a case study of Dawakin – Tofa Local

Government Area (LGA) of Kano State. The research study would also consider the benefits of infrastructural development as well as the types of mechanisms used in practice to estimate its impact.

The objectives of the study include the following:

- a. To estimate to what extent investment in rural infrastructure contributes to socio – economic development, and ultimately, improves Nigeria"s GDP.
- b. To ascertain the relationship between infrastructure development and economic growth in Dawakin-Tofa LGA of Kano State.
- c. Identify the key challenges and constraints in infrastructure experienced by the people of Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions which this research study would attempt to answer.: a. How much infrastructure does Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State need?

- b. In what ways does infrastructure influence socio - economic activities in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State?
- c. What are the socio – economic development contributions of infrastructural facilities in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State?
- d. Is there any increase or decrease in personal income among the residents of Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State as a result of available infrastructure?
- e. Does infrastructure improve the productivity of workers and farmers?

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study will look at socio – economic infrastructural development in Nigeria"s rural area as a panacea for improving Nigeria"s GDP, a case study of Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State. The general state of infrastructure would be considered. Additionally, a sampled population of 150 respondents in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State and cutting across the wards was assessed. Furthermore, socio – economic infrastructures bordering on road (transportation), education, water, energy and health facilities/services would be considered in this research.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Thirwall (2014), the economic and social development of the world"s poorest countries is probably the greatest challenge facing societies in recent times. Over one billion of the world"s estimated seven billion live in abject poverty; the same number suffer from various degrees of degradation, water, health care or education. The economic growth of countries refers to the increase in output of goods and services that a country produces over a year. In that line therefore, societies are to set development targets for themselves. Development programmes and plans should be designed and implemented giving attention to the exact needs of those at the grassroots. This is however not the case in most developing countries, Nigeria in particular.

Willis (2005) outlined certain „Development targets" which are:

- a. Halving the proportion of people whose income is less than US\$1 a day;
- b. Reducing by two – thirds the maternal mortality rate;
- c. Reducing the incidence of malaria and other major diseases; and
- d. Reducing the proportion of people without sustainable access to safe drinking water and basic sanitation. It is believed that infrastructural development within the world's developing countries has not received the will and acceptable attention of consecutive governments, particularly in Nigeria and Africa as a whole. It therefore should form an integral part of the policies of any Government.

Most local governments in Nigeria could be termed as having the characteristics of rural settlements. The nature of development in these places cannot be compared to having the form of the urban. One of the characteristics of such a place is the occupation of the people of the area, which is agriculture and trading. On that premise therefore, Dawakin – Tofa can be termed to have the characteristics of a rural area. Just like most rural areas, residents of the Area engage in primary activities involving agriculture, trading and mining amongst others. The Local Government is the third tier of governance in the country. It is the closest tier of governance to the people. In spite of the important contribution the third tier of government makes towards the economic development of the nation, it has been neglected in terms of infrastructural development which has made it non – attractive to live in and also increase poverty in the rural areas. This is justified by the high correlation that exists between rural living and poverty with this situation particularly exacerbated in developing countries (World Bank, 1994). Adequate and qualitative infrastructure gives a country an advantage in terms of improved regional and international trade and significantly enhances the economic growth and development of a country and consequently alleviates poverty.

Countries that have been termed as „First World countries“ or most developed nations of the world prioritize infrastructural improvements. Western Europe developed sporadically due to the large investments and priority given to infrastructure. These infrastructures were to enhance the industrial revolution, manufacturing industries and everything associated with it. One of the first infrastructural items to have been improved upon was transportation. Transportation is therefore a major infrastructure in Nigeria's LGAs, more so that these Areas are usually far from the central areas (urban environment). The authors went further to state that “man, nations, regions, cities, towns and the world would be severely limited in development and GDP output without transportation, which is a key factor for physical and economic growth.”

Most people in Kano, especially those living within the scope of this research are predominantly into agriculture and trading as means of livelihood. Abubakar et al (2019) sought to identify the means of transportation used by farmers to convey their farm produce and to examine the problems of transporting agricultural produce in Ungogo LGA of Kano State. The study revealed that the condition of the roads was critical; the roads in the study area are characterized by seasonality due to the persistent deterioration of roads by erosion and poor maintenance by authorities concerned. The authors suggested the need for the

construction of roads and bridges to make rural areas to all weather accessible and government should engage in construction of more feeder roads in rural areas that will link the different farms in the area to the markets. In the area of transportation and its impact on economic growth, an efficient transport system which offers cost, time and reliability advantage would permit goods to be moved quickly from one point to the other. It is worth to state that the local government as well as most other rural areas is usually confronted with the challenge of transportation. This limitation affects their ability to reduce their poverty, and in order to satisfy their need for greater access to health, education and every possible opportunity, ease of physical accessibility and freedom of movement are top priorities. Unfortunately, the transportation system needed to evacuate these goods and services are not available and adequate. Additionally, other infrastructures such as water, health care services amongst others are not readily available.

Gnade et al (2016) in their work on the impact of basic and social infrastructure on economic growth revealed that insufficient infrastructure in informal settlements is a major obstacle to economic development. It was further revealed that infrastructural investment and economic growth had a strong positive relationship. In an attempt to make a case for power infrastructure development in the socio – economic situations in Sub – Sahara Africa (SSA), Ngcobo et al (2019) revealed that the “expenditures in infrastructure development was the highest in emerging and developing countries, especially when juxtaposed with other countries, India and China in particular. Developed nations of the world have one distinct similarity – remaining above the subsistence economic growth through the secured access to electricity delivered to its citizens (World Bank, 2000a). South Africa is reputed to have the most efficient power supply in Africa, generating over 20,000MW of electricity. Nigeria on the other hand, generates between 3,000 to 4,000 MW and depends largely on hydro form of power generation. This is grossly inadequate for the domestic consumption of its teeming population of an estimated 180 million people talk less of meeting the economic demands of the country.

Efficient power infrastructural development therefore is a prerequisite for economic growth, improved competition, industrialization and earned recognition and induction into the global economy (Oshikoya, 2008). Only 58% of Nigerians have access to electricity. It is estimated that between 2000 – 2018, Nigeria had lost about US\$470 billion in GDP due to under – investment in power infrastructure (Arowolo et al, 2019). Morris & Fessehaie (2014) in their research

findings observed, “when infrastructure is poor and commodity extraction is based in remote locations, local supply firms face high marketing and distribution barrier, having to either incur high costs to relocate their businesses, or travel to meet buyers, and arrange transport of supply products or services. Infrastructure planning and investment must be responsive to the development priorities of a country or sub – region. Infrastructural development is an agent for growth and the narrowing of development gaps (Prakesh, 2018).

Infrastructural development in rural Nigeria has the potential of increasing Nigeria's GDP as it did at independence when the primary sector contributed about 70% (Chete et al, 2013) to the country's GDP. Li et al (2019) emphasized on the imperative of investing in power infrastructure as being a catalyst in China's economic growth. The research stressed that the huge investment which China made in the area of energy infrastructure was highly responsible for the country's socio – economic growth. Nigeria's power generation disappointingly is what a Chinese manufacturing firm needs for its production. The research further recommended the need for all developing nations to invest in energy infrastructure. The poverty and underdevelopment in most rural areas in Africa and Nigeria in particular is as a result of the inhibiting relationship between them and the urban areas (Matunhu, 2011).

A sound rural economy is a prerequisite for a sound urban economy (Langeweg et al, 2000). The two forms of settlement cannot do without the other. While the urban area depends on the rural area for most of its agricultural (primary goods needed in the manufacturing industries, the rural areas depend on the urban areas for markets, introduction of infrastructure for the enhancement of the socio – economic well – being of the area. Trading activities boost GDP. Gaal & Afrah (2017) supported this opinion when they pointed out that, "Infrastructural services support trade whether or not they themselves are traded. Lack of infrastructure in any society would therefore lead to poor standard of living, economic deficit, decline in productivity and free trade barriers."

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this study is survey research, which serves as a blueprint for carrying out this research work. According to Ngu (2005) and Bhartti (2014), a research design can be viewed as a plan on how to study what has been earmarked for the study to investigate. The design helps in determining the current status of the phenomenon under investigation. The choice of this design stems from the fact that it permits the studying of small portions of a large population with the aim of making generalization. Furthermore, it permits the use of primary sources of data.

This research was designed to examine the impact of economic infrastructural development in Nigeria's rural area as a panacea for improving Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product, a case study of Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State. To achieve this, independent variables such as school, electricity (energy), market, road and health care were considered. They were analyzed with a view to establishing their relationship with the dependent variable: socio – economic development.

Population of the Study

Population is any group of individuals that have one or more characteristics in common which are of interest to the researcher. The population of the study consists of the residents of Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State. It is pertinent to state that a sampled population of 150 people across the LGA was considered.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A purposive (also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective) sampling technique was used for the study. It is a form of non – probability sampling. According to Amin (2005), purposive sampling technique is the type of sampling where the researcher uses his/her judgment or common sense regarding participants from whom the information was collected. Purposive sampling technique was used in order to choose the respondents who were believed to have information concerning the study by using their own judgment, and then questionnaire was distributed to the respondents. Additionally, purposive sampling was used because the researcher wanted to get the key aim and objectives of this research. The sample size of 150 questionnaires was distributed to both sexes in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State.

Instrument for Data Collection

In sourcing for the primary data, questionnaire was administered and distributed to the sampled population for responses. The distributed questionnaire had two sections. Section A is for demographic characteristics while Section B was for the information required for the research. The questionnaire was designed with the question in statement from which respondents were given the chance to tick the responses of their choice.

Method of Data Analysis

The method of data analysis in the study is descriptive statistics. Statistical tools used were percentages, and table frequencies. This method was chosen because it was proved to be adequate for effective analysis of the data generated for the study.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State, Nigeria is located between Latitude 11^o23'26" and 11^o58'11" N and Longitude 7^o15'00" and 8^o11'59" E (Abubakar et al, 2019 & Yusha"u et al, 2015. The LGA lies on an area size of 479km². The study area is bordered to the East by Minjibir and Ungogo Local Governments; to the South by Tofa Local Government; to the West by Bagwai Local Government and to the North by Bichi and Makoda Local Governments. The sampled villages and towns among the 38 major districts in the study area are Tattarawa, Ganduje, Jemomi, Marke, Dungurawa, Jalli, Dawakin – Tofa, Tumfafi, Danguguwa and Dawanau (Abdulazeez & Adamu, 2019).

Data Presentation and Analysis

Section A: Socio – Demographic Bio – Data

Table 4.3.1: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	87	69.0 31.0	69.0 31.0	69.0
Valid Female	39			100
Total	126	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.1 shows the gender distribution of 126 respondents. It is clearly observed that majority of the respondents participated in the field survey. The table further reveals that 69.0% of the respondents were male, while 31.0% were females. This shows that majority of the respondents in the survey were males. This is however not a balanced representation of the sampled population. While the figure for male is considered acceptable and sufficient as argued by Sekaran (2015) that 50% is suitable for a survey, which for female is not suitable as it is below 50%.

Table 4.3.2: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18 – 24 years	22	17.5	17.5 46.8	17.5 46.8
25 – 31 years	59	46.8	25.4	25.4
32 – 38 years	32	25.4		
Valid 39 years and above	13	10.3	10.3	10.3
Total	126	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.2 shows that majority of respondents between 25 – 31 years were the highest distribution which constitutes 46.8% of the respondents. This was followed by respondents within the age gap of 32 – 38 years which reflects 25.4% of the respondents from the sampled population. This analysis has confirmed the 2006 Nigerian population census which indicated that the Nigerian youth population constituted more than half of the total population of the country. It has further indicated that the work force in most Nigerian societies falls within the youthful age bracket. This is very good for a developing country such as Nigeria, with its attendant preponderant economic resources. It further shows that if such a population is well utilized, it has the potential of rescuing the country from its erstwhile poor state of economic development. It also reveals that for some years to come, Nigeria would still have a larger part of its population within the working bracket. It thus further positions the country to achieve its much desired goal of economic revamping and bolstering the country’s GDP.

Table 4.3.3: Marital Status

Respondents were asked to indicate their marital status and their responses are tabulated in the table below:

Table 4.3.3: Marital Status of Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Single	45	35.7	35.7	35.7
Married	68	54.0	54.0	89.7
Valid				
Divorced	13	10.3	10.3	
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

From Table 4.3.3, it can be seen that majority of those that participated in the survey research were married which constituted 54.0% of the respondents while 35.7% of the respondents were single and 10.3% of the respondents were divorced. This revealed that married people constituted the majority of the respondents both from the rural people and staff of the LGA Secretariat. One possible explanation for this phenomenon could be that in the northern part of Nigeria, people get married earlier than those from the southern part of the country, mostly due to religious inclinations.

Table 4.3.4: Educational Qualification of Respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
SSCE	24	19.0	43.7	19.0 62.7
ND/NCE	55	25.4	25.4	88.1
BA/BSc/BEng/BTech/HND	32	11.9	11.9	
Others, please specify	15			
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.4 reveals that majority of the respondents possessed ND/NCE which constituted 43.7% of the respondents, followed by those with BA/BSc/BTech/BEng/BEd/HND and this constituted 25.4% of the respondents while SSCE holders were 19.0% of the total number of the respondents. Other academic qualifications possessed by some of the respondents include Post Graduate Diploma and Masters which constituted 11.9% of the respondents. This implies that majority of the respondents were those that possessed ND/NCE academic qualification. This fraction represents 43.7% of the respondents that was sampled.

Table 4.3.5: Occupation of Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Farming	48	38.1	30.2	38.1
Trading	38	9.5	9.5	
Civil Servant	12	14.3	14.3	61.9
Others, please specify	18	7.9	7.9	
	10			

Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0
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Source: Researcher"s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.5 shows that majority of the respondents were into farming as a source of livelihood. This represented 38.1% of the respondents that had returned their questionnaire. 30.2% were into trading activities; 9.5% (12) of the respondents were into teaching while 18 people (14.3%) were civil servants and 10 (7.9%) of the respondents were into other forms of occupation such as banking, students, technicians, amongst others. This analysis affirms with Brenner (1970), Sabiu et al (2018) & Adegboye (2016) on the typical forms of livelihood engaged in by people living in the rural areas. Realizing that the major occupation of the people of Dawakin – Tofa LGA is farming, in the development planning of the area, the government would most likely consider areas that would be beneficial to them infrastructurally. The infrastructures should be able to enhance the productivity level of the people. It therefore becomes crucial for Government to develop infrastructures that would enhance agricultural production of the Area.

Section B: Activities of Infrastructure on the Socio – economic Development of Dawakin – Tofa Local Government Area of Kano State

Table 4.3.6: Respondents on if they believed Kano State Government is able to provide necessary socio – economic infrastructures for the residents of Dawakin – Tofa LGA

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	72	57.1	57.1 20.6	57.1
No	26	20.6	22.2	100.0
Not Sure	28	22.2		
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher"s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.6 shows on the question of if respondents believed that Kano State Government was able to provide necessary socio – economic infrastructures, 72(57.1%) of the respondents answered "Yes". On the other hand, 26(20.6%) of the respondents gave the answer, "No" to the question while 28 (22.2%) of the respondents were not sure. This analysis shows that most of the respondents were optimistic about the Government of Kano State"s ability to provide necessary socio – economic infrastructures for the residents of Dawakin – Tofa LGA.

Table 4.3.7: Which of these infrastructures is of greater importance to your socio – economic well – being?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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School (Education)	16	12.7	12.7 28.6	12.7
Hospital	36	28.6	25.4	
Electricity	32	25.4		100.0
Road (Transportation)	42	33.3	33.3	
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

From table 4.3.7, 16(12.7%) respondents pointed out that School (Education) was of greater importance to their socio -economic well – being. Other respondents, totalling 36, which represents 28.6% of the sampled population opined that provision of hospital infrastructures was of greater importance to them than others. Thirty – two (25.4%) respondents believed that Electricity was of greater importance to their socio – economic well – being. A total of 42(33.3%) respondents however pointed out that Road (transportation) infrastructures were of greater importance to them. This analysis suggests that while on an average most respondents see all infrastructures as being of great importance, most respondents suggested that Road infrastructure was of greater importance to their socio – economic well – being. It also reveals that most rural people are in pressing need of roads for effective movement of their agricultural produce from the point of production (farms) to the urban areas and markets. Roads are of essential value for wider development ends, such as poverty reduction, and improved standard of living of the people.

Table 4.3.8: To what extent do available infrastructures in Dawakin – Tofa LGA contribute to socio – economic activities?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly	68	54.0	54.0 35.0	54.0
Not sure	44	35.0	11.0	
No effect	14	11.0		100.0
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.8 shows that majority of the respondents amounting to 68(54.0%) felt strongly that the available infrastructures in Dawakin – Tofa LGA contributed to socio – economic activities. On the other hand, 44(35.0%) were not sure of the impact of available infrastructures while 14(11.0%) of the respondents felt that the available infrastructures had no effect in contributing to socio – economic activities. From the analysis of data collected from respondents, Kano’s unprecedented socio – economic activities when compared to other neighbouring states has always been as a result of the State’s available infrastructures (Dankani, 2013).

Table 4.3.9: Is there a relationship between infrastructures and socio-economic growth in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	79	62.7	62.7	62.7
No	37	29.4	29.4	
Not sure	10	7.9	7.9	100.0
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

From Table 4.3.9, it can be clearly seen that 79 (62.7%) of the respondents agreed that there is a relationship between socio – economic growth in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State. It also reveals that 37 people, constituting 29.4% disagreed, while 10(7.9%) were not sure if there was a relationship between infrastructures and socio-economic growth in Dawakin – Tofa LGA.

Table 4.3.10: Is there any increase or decrease in your personal income as a resident of Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State arising from the availability of certain infrastructures?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Increase	66	52.4	52.4	52.4
No	42	33.3	33.3	100.0
Not sure	18	14.3	14.3	
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.10 shows that majority of the respondents agreed that there was an increase in personal income among residents of Dawakin – Tofa LGA, which constituted 52.4% of the respondents, while 33.33% of the respondents disagreed. On the other hand, 14.3% of the same respondents were not sure if there was an increase in the personal income of the residents. From the analysis, it is worth to note that provision of infrastructures has contributed in increasing the personal income of the residents of Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State. Availability of infrastructures have been the major contributory factor in the development of most parts of the world today, especially those that have been termed as being the most developed parts of the world.

Table 4.3.11: Do you agree that provision of infrastructures in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State has brought about socio – economic development?

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Yes	87	69.0	69.0	69.0
Valid No	39	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.11 shows that majority of the respondents agreed that provision of infrastructures in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State has brought about economic development. This constituted 87(69.0%) of the total number of respondents. On the other hand, 39 respondents which constitute 31.0% of the respondents disagreed.

Table 4.3.12: Respondents on what are the socio – economic contribution of infrastructure in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
It has improved business in the State.	38	30.2	30.2	30.2
It has improved agricultural sector.	29	23.0	23.0	53.2
Valid It improved general standard of living in the area.	17	13.5	13.5	66.7
All of the above.	42	33.3	33.3	
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.12 reveals that majority of the respondents that participated in this survey research believed that infrastructure in the study area brought about an improvement in business, agriculture and standard of living in Dawakin – Tofa LGA. This constituted 33.3% of the respondents.

Table 4.3.13: Respondents on how they rate Kano State Government in provision of infrastructures and economic development in Dawakin – Tofa LGA of Kano State

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Excellent	27	21.4	21.4	21.4
Good	51	40.5	40.5	61.9
Valid Fair	37	29.4	29.4	91.3
Poor	11	8.7	8.7	100.0
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

From table 4.3.13, it can be seen that while 27(21.4%) of the respondents opined that the effort of Kano State Government (KSG) has been excellent in provision of infrastructures and economic development in Dawakin – Tofa LGA. Majority of the respondents believed that it has been good. On the other hand, 37 (29.4%) respondents pointed out that the effort of the KSG has been fair, while 11 (8.7%) believed that the Government’s effort has only been poor.

Table 4.3.14: Respondents on the need for government to set up committee which involves the rural members and ministry for rural development towards addressing the issue of infrastructure

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	58	46.0	46.0	46.0
Valid				100.0
No	68	54.0	54.0	
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Study, 2021

Table 4.3.14 shows that majority of the respondents disagreed that there was no need for government to set up a committee which involves the rural members and ministry for rural development towards addressing the issues of infrastructure. This constitutes 68 (54.0%) of the respondents while 58 (46.0%) of the respondents agreed that there was need for government to set up committee. The implication from this analysis is that the government is already doing a convincing job in the provision of adequate infrastructures for the people of Dawakin – Tofa and Kano State as a whole.

Table 4.3.15: Respondents on which infrastructure has been more beneficial to the people of Dawakin – Tofa LGA

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Road infrastructure	44	34.9	34.9	34.9
School	31	24.6	15.9	
Water	20	15.9		
Valid				100.0
Hospital	15	11.9	11.9	
Power (Electricity)	9	7.1	7.1	
Market	7	5.6	5.6	

Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0
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Source: Researcher"s Field Study, 2021

From table 4.3.15, it can be seen that on the issue of which of the infrastructures has been more beneficial to the people of Dawakin – Tofa LGA, respondents pointed out that road infrastructure was more beneficial to the communities, which constitutes 34.9%. This was followed by schools which constitutes 24.6% while 20(15.9%) of the respondents believed that water was more beneficial to them. A total of 15(11.9%) of the respondents believed hospitals had been more beneficial to them. Power (Electricity) in the opinion of 9 respondents (7.1%) was more beneficial to the communities, while 7 respondents (5.6%) believed that market infrastructure was more beneficial to them.

Table 4.3.16: Respondents on the challenges Kano State Government is facing in providing infrastructures for the socio – economic development of Dawakin – Tofa LGA

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Lack of funds	38	30.2	30.2	30.2
Corruption	49	38.9	38.9	100.0
Valid Misplacement of Priority	13	10.3	10.3	
Poor management	16	12.7	12.7	
All of the above	10	7.9	7.9	
Total	126	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher"s Field Study, 2021

From table 4.3.16, it can be clearly seen that most respondents that participated in this research survey believed corruption was the main challenge Kano State Government was facing in terms of providing infrastructures for the socio – economic development of Dawakin – Tofa LGA which constituted 49(38.9%) of the respondents. This is followed by 38 (30.2%) of the respondents who suggested that lack of funds was the challenge while 16(12.7%) of the respondents pointed out that poor management; 13(10.3%) respondents were of the opinion that misplacement of priority was the main challenge. Meanwhile, 9 respondents, constituting 7.1% submitted that all of the above were the challenges being faced by the Kano State Government in providing infrastructures for the socio – economic development of Dawakin – Tofa LGA.

CONCLUSION

Development of socio – economic infrastructure has been generally deduced to have great impact on the economy. In Nigeria"s rural areas, the predominant sources of livelihood are farming and trading. These are age-long sources of livelihoods which in time past have led to the economic growth of most societies.

At the early stage of Europe's industrialization, the development of socio – economic infrastructures succeeded in spurring economic growth. It enhanced the diversification of the economy of most European countries at the time and also contributing in ending colonialism. It is thus believed that diversifying Nigeria's economy from over dependence on crude oil to other sectors would require investment in the development and provision of socio – economic infrastructures, especially to Nigeria's rural areas, where these infrastructures are seriously lacking.

The development in infrastructures would not only boost economic growth but it would contribute to the alleviation of poverty and over dependence on foreign economies. It is hoped that Nigerian governments at all levels would begin to consider the important roles of infrastructures in boosting the GDP of the country and also form a more important relationship with the third tier of government in the provision of necessary socio – economic infrastructure for the people at that level. It is also expected that Government at all level would provide such infrastructures based on the real needs of the people. In so doing, there would be economic gains on the money spent by such Government. This study adds voice on the need for the Nigerian Government to improve on already existing socio – economic infrastructures. Improving on the existing infrastructures would no doubt improve the total GDP of the country.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- a. Government should provide more electricity to the rural communities in order to boost socio – economic activities.
- b. Government should provide more market facilities in the rural areas. This would facilitate economic activities, create jobs and generally boost GDP and alleviate poverty.
- c. It is imperative for Government at all levels to conduct research on the most important needs of the people before enunciating infrastructural items in those Areas.

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